

Sex Crime and The Media: Sex Offending and The Press in a Divided Society

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2653

Impact Factor: 4.012

Citation:

Murugeswari, K. “Sex Crime and The Media: Sex Offending and The Press in a Divided Society.” *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 81–85.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2599844>

K.Murugeswari, M.Sc., M.Ed.,

Assistant Professor in Biological Science

Abstract

Sex crime has become one of the most intense areas of public and political concern in recent decades. Media representations give important clues as to how we should perceive the nature and extent of sex crime, how we should think and feel about it, how we should respond to it, and the measures that might be taken to reduce risk. Understanding the media construction of sex crime is central to understanding its meaning and place in our everyday lives. The study shows how increased market competition and tabloidisation has altered fundamentally the way in which news is produced, communicated and consumed discusses representations of the full range of sex crimes from consensual homosexual offences and prostitution to serial rape and sex murder draws upon extensive empirical research in India, while addressing issues relevant to advance capitalist societies across the globe.

Introduction

In media representations, the term sex crimes most frequently refer to rape and child sexual abuse, although it can include a wider range of acts such as exhibitionism and voyeurism. While the majority of these crimes receive little media attention, certain sensational sex crimes are prominent topics in news and entertainment media. Media attention tends to focus on violent crimes committed by “dangerous” strangers, largely defined as poor men of colour, and crimes committed against white and middle-class victims. These representations provide a distorted image of the reality of sex crimes, which most frequently occur in private settings, by someone known to the victim. Media coverage has also been criticized for focusing on the actions and responsibility of victims, suggesting that victim behaviour, such as drinking, flirting, or being in the “wrong place at the wrong time” precipitates sexual violence. Sex crimes have become a highly controversial and contested area, and media coverage reflects this, sometimes supporting progressive social and cultural change and sometimes providing a vehicle for “backlash” sentiments. Social media has been a driver of changes in the media landscape around sexual violence in recent years has provided a new forum for survivors to disseminate their stories but has also been marked by online harassment and abuse.

Sex Crime Law and Legal Definition

Sex crimes refer to criminal offences of a sexual nature. Commonly known sex crimes include, rape, child molestation, sexual battery, lewd conduct, possession and distribution of child pornography, possession and distribution of obscene material, prostitution, solicitation of prostitution, pimping, pandering, indecent exposure, lewd act with a child.

Sex Offenders

A sexual offender can be any gender, any race, any religion, any age, and also any social class. A sexual offender is an individual who commits a crime that is considered to be sexually as legally defined in his or her own legal jurisdiction. A sexual offence involves participating in illegal sexual behaviour (this is defined by criminal statutes). It is important to be aware that there are major differences throughout the world in regards as to what is considered as a sexual; every place has different laws and regulations. Paraphilia is an erotosexual condition that can occur in both men and women react to, or rely on, any irregular or socially insufferable stimulus in either imagery or fantasy for erotic-sexual arousal and the achievement of an orgasm.

Characteristics of Persistent Sexual Offenders

A meta-analysis of eight-two recidivism studies (1,620 findings from 29,450 sexual offenders) identified various sexual presences and antisocial orientation, which is considered to be predictors of sexual recidivism for both adults and adolescent sexual offenders. Some of the active risk factors that could be useful to treatment targets are sexual preoccupations and general self-regulation problems. Elements that are usually brought up and addressed in sexual offender programs (psychological distress, denial of sex crime, victim empathy, stated motivation for treatment) had either little or no relationship with sexual and violent recidivism.

Juvenile Sexual Offenders

Youths between the ages of 12-18 who have been either officially charged with a sexual crime or have performed an act that could be officially charged, or committed sexually abusive and/or aggressive behaviour are those who are considered to be juvenile sexual offenders. Some examples of a sexual crime can include child molestation, rape, exhibitionism, voyeurism.

Assessments for juvenile sexual offenders is a procedure of information collections. The information will include evaluations conducted by psychologists, psychiatrists, social workers or other to develop successful intervention strategies for that specific juvenile, making placement choices, and/or informing legal or social service agencies if necessary. The treatment of juveniles is a set of different interventions based on a specialized assessment that can include psychotherapy, family therapy, medical treatments, or other psychical interventions. Probation supervision and residential placement are not considered treatment for this specific age group. However, they are still important aspects of intervention with juvenile sexual offenders.

Silence and Sensationalism

Sexual violence has historically been a taboo topic, marked by silence and denial. At the same time, sensationalized reporting of a small number of cases of sexual violence has been a feature of media reporting at least since the inception of mass newspapers sexual violence often masks deep-seated silences about the most common conditions under which sex crimes occur and the effects on their victims. Surette’s “law of opposites,” where media representations of crime are almost directly opposite to statistical realities, is particularly true in the case of sex crimes (Surette, 1998). While media representations typically depict attacks by violent strangers, that the vast majority of

crimes of a sexual nature are committed by intimates or acquaintances. These crimes are largely hidden; extremely under-reported, and often not recognized as crimes at all.

The disproportionate focus on sex crimes committed by strangers is accompanied by significant differences in the extent and nature of media coverage given to crimes committed against victims of different races and social classes. Far more media attention is given to middle- and upper-class victims, and to victims from dominant racial and ethnic groups, while sexual assaults against victims from lower-class or minority ethnic backgrounds are largely ignored. At the same time, mainstream media tend to over-represent perpetrators from lower-class and minority racial and ethnic backgrounds, reinforcing stereotypes of ethnic and lower-class male criminality and misrepresenting the realities and dangers of sexual violence.

Representations of Rape

Rape, or sexual assault, is the most archetypal of sex crimes, and the one most subject to media misreporting. Media responses to rape have historically been dominated by what have come to be known as a series of “rape myths.” myths produce a distorted understanding of sexual violence that sees some types of rape as more harmful or “real” than others, and that reinforces gender, racial, and class stereotypes to deny legitimacy to certain victims and falsely label minority ethnic and lower-class men as more prone to commit sexual violence.

Child Sexual Assault

Child sexual abuse was, before the 1970s, deemed to be rare and the province of “perverted” strangers. In the 1970s, however, feminist activists began to draw attention to the prevalence of child sexual abuse alongside their campaigns around adult sexual assault.

Since that time, the issue of child sexual assault has been subject to highly sensational reporting around the danger of “pedophilic” strangers. In many ways this mirrors the media misrepresentation of rape, with the emphasis on “stranger danger” obscuring the fact that the vast majority of perpetrators are family members or close acquaintances of the victims (Furedi, 2013; Jewkes & Wykes, 2012).

The Dangers of Social Media and Child Sex Crimes

Social media sites with easy access for children, as well as predators, are creating a high risk for dangerous child sex crimes. Social media has increased incidents of child abductions, sex trafficking, pornography, and sexual assaults against children.

Social Media Sites Increase Risks

Due to advances in technology and easy online access, the number of children who spend daily time on the internet and social media sites is increasing day-by-day. The number of online predators who are seeking young victims is also increasing each day. According to studies, 96% of teenagers use social media sites like Facebook, Snap Chat, MySpace, Tinder, Instagram, and Kik daily. Over 60% of children between the ages of 13 and 17 have at least one profile posted on a social networking site where they spend more than two hours each day.

Online research shows that 99% of children between the ages of 12 and 15 spend time on social media sites. In 2013, the average time spent online for 12-15-year-old children was 17 hours a week. Studies also show that 96% of children between the ages of 8 and 11, and 82% of children between the ages of 5 and 7 spend daily time on social networking sites. A 24-hour lawyer who handles criminal sex cases sees crimes perpetrated against children even young than five.

Sex Offences by Computer Committed with Children

The Internet has attracted many of the children most vulnerable to predators. After identifying a victim, the predator, sometimes posing on-line as a teenager, then tries to develop a relationship that can turn sexual. Some states have laws, which vary by state, governing the use of a computer to lure or entice child for sexual purposes. Such laws generally apply if the computer transmission involved originated in or was received in the state.

In general, a person is guilty of solicitation of a child by a computer if the person is an adult and the person knowingly, with the intent to commit an unlawful sex act, entices, induces, persuades, seduces, prevails, advises, coerces, or orders, by means of a computer, a minor, to meet with the defendant or any other person for the purpose of engaging in sexual intercourse, sodomy, or to engage in a sexual performance, obscene sexual performance, or sexual conduct for his or her benefit. It may also be a crime to transmit obscene material to a child using any computer communication system allowing the input, output, examination, or transfer of computer programs obscene material for the purpose of initiating or engaging in sexual acts with the child.

Online Predators

In the past three years, the number of online sexual predators and offences seen by criminal lawyers has more than doubled. Investigations and arrests show that 82% of child sex crimes originate from online social media sites where predators gain knowledge of their victims’ likes and habits. According to FBI child crime investigations, over 65% of online sex offenders use social media sites to gain information about a victim’s home and school activities, daily schedule or location, and friend networks.

Although both males and females are at risk, statistics show that 75% of sex crimes initiated over the internet is against young girls between the ages of 12 and 15. Since online predators commonly disguise their age and identity with fake photos of attractive young males, preteen and teenage girls often think they are talking to a cute, interested boy within their peer group. Both males and females in this age group are particularly vulnerable to predators involved in sexual assaults, child pornography, and sex trafficking and prostitution.

Conclusion

Overall, this paper has documented the profound harm and sheer costs of sexual assault. While people and communities do and will recover from sexual assault, sexual assault is a trauma that is preventable, and significantly more effort needs to be made in this direction. It is simply not good enough for sexual assault to continue to be largely privatised and a taboo topic. Awareness-raising about these issues needs to be such that talking about sexual assault becomes commonplace. Strategies to prevent sexual assault need to be increased, including strategies that focus on creating greater respect for women and other disempowered people, and on communicating the social unacceptability of all violence. Non-violence should be promoted as a fundamental social and community value.

Web Sources

1. https://books.google.com/books/about/Sex_Crime_and_the_Media.html?id=1OK_Gd_YG_t_fAAC
2. <http://oxfordre.com/criminology/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264079.001.0001/acrefore-9780190264079-e-118>.

3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Association_for_the_Treatment_of_Sexual_Offenders
4. <https://morning.pk/story/7342>
5. <https://kellerlawoffices.com/dangers-of-social-media/>
6. <https://definitions.uslegal.com/s/sex-offenses-by-computer-committed-with-children/>
7. <https://aifs.gov.au/publications/ripple-effects-sexual-assault/conclusion>